

The Contribution of Cooperatives to the Development of Mongolia's Market Economy

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1. International cooperative movement

The centralization of production and supply within the framework of market economy development presents an opportunity for addressing societal needs and advancing science and technology. However, it also results in an uneven distribution of wealth, giving rise to various adverse consequences such as inflation, unemployment, poverty, greenhouse gas emissions, and environmental pollution. In response to these challenges, there is a pressing need to devise solutions that counteract the excessive concentration of the economy and encourage the active participation of individual members of society in wealth creation. Various approaches and organizational structures, including individual entrepreneurship, partnerships, and farming initiatives, can be explored to tackle this issue. Among these options, one rational solution involves the integration of household enterprises into business operations through the establishment and development of cooperatives. This has led to the formation of cooperatives as a distinct form of business organization, serving as a means to mitigate the negative impacts associated with economic concentration and promote a more inclusive approach to wealth creation.

At the close of the 19th century, as economic crises deepened and the wealth gap widened in developed nations, individuals from impoverished and low-income backgrounds sought a means to generate income through collaboration. This initiative laid the foundation for the emergence of the International Cooperative Movement. The roots of the cooperative movement are often traced back to 1844 in Manchester, England, where a group of workers voluntarily united to establish a worker's cooperative. They shared profits and income to enhance their living conditions. Contrary to this account, historical records of French and German cooperatives suggest an earlier origin. As early as 1789, French workers, guided by the initiative of French social democrats, established a small production cooperative. Simultaneously, in Germany, Hermann Schultz, the mayor of Delitzze, founded a credit cooperative. While the Manchester example is well-documented, these instances highlight that cooperative efforts may have begun earlier in different European regions. Regardless of the specific origin, cooperatives in Europe initially operated in various sectors such as small handicrafts, artels, trade, supply, finance, and credit. Remarkably, these cooperative sectors have persisted and remained largely unchanged to the present day.

The necessity for collaborative efforts among various nations in the realm of cooperatives led to the establishment of the first International Association of Cooperatives, known as the Alliance, in 1895. This marked the beginning of collective problem-solving through a unified organization. Over time, the International Cooperative Alliance has evolved into a prestigious global entity, bringing together cooperative organizations from over 200 countries, boasting a membership of more than 800 million individuals. Mongolia actively participates as a member of this Alliance, contributing to the cooperative movement on an international scale.

Since 2012, the United Nations Sustainable Development Group has annually released rankings of countries based on their sustainable economic development. The criteria include per capita income, public attitudes towards society, beliefs, living conditions, education, freedom, health, and public spending on social consumption. According to this ongoing study, Finland has consistently held the top position for three consecutive years, with Norway also frequently ranking highly. Sweden consistently secures a spot in the top 5, while Switzerland, Denmark, the Netherlands, France, and Canada regularly make it into the top 10.

Reflecting on this analysis, a group of European scientists has concluded that stable and accessible economic development is closely interconnected with people's psychology and social relationships, seen as equally crucial as financial resources and property. The researchers advocate for the promotion of small businesses, particularly in the form of cooperatives, as a significant contributor to sustainable economic development. This perspective underscores the importance of psychological and social factors alongside traditional economic indicators in achieving stability and progress. Research has also delved into international cooperative movements and countries where cooperative enterprises thrive. According to a report [1] by G. Enkhbat, New Zealand, France, the Netherlands, Finland, Sweden, Luxembourg, Germany, Italy, Denmark, and Poland emerge as some of the top 10 countries with well-established cooperative economies globally. Notably, products generated within the cooperative sector in these countries contribute significantly, constituting 14-20 percent of their respective Gross Domestic Products (GDP). This highlights the considerable economic impact and significance of cooperatives in these nations.

The findings from the research released by the United Nations align with the observation that countries excelling in Sustainable Economic Development rankings also tend to be among the top 10 nations with thriving cooperative sectors. This substantiates the conclusion drawn by scientists, emphasizing the pivotal role of cooperatives in fostering sustainable social development. In contemporary times, cooperative farming is gaining international traction across various sectors, including agriculture, food production, trade, financial and credit services, supply, construction, housing, energy, education, health, and social domains. This highlights the diverse and expanding impact of cooperatives on a global scale, spanning a wide range of essential industries and services.

Mongolian scientist B. Bayarmaa has put forth a significant proposal advocating for the establishment of an indicator system that encompasses production, technology, savings, green development, people's livelihood, and satisfaction. This proposal stems from the recognition that relying solely on the growth of the gross domestic product (GDP) may not adequately capture the comprehensive social and economic conditions of a country [2]. Bayarmaa's suggestion highlights the need for a more nuanced and inclusive set of indicators to gauge a nation's overall well-being, considering factors beyond mere economic output. This proposal reflects a growing acknowledgment in academic and policy circles that a more holistic approach is essential for a thorough understanding of a country's social and economic landscape.

Studies conducted by scientists indicate that countries with well-developed cooperatives experience a notable difference in both the quantity and quality of jobs. In comparison to countries that place less emphasis on cooperatives, those with a strong cooperative presence show a 15-20 percent higher employment standard. Remarkably, in Austria, Finland, and Sweden, approximately 50% of the population holds membership in cooperatives. These cooperatives play a crucial role in creating employment opportunities, particularly benefiting individuals from vulnerable social groups and people with disabilities. The findings underscore the positive impact of cooperative structures not only on the economy but also on fostering inclusive and diverse employment environments.

Cooperatives offer various advantages, which encompass key principles such as:

- **Voluntary Open Membership:** Cooperatives operate on the principle of voluntary and open membership, allowing individuals to join based on their willingness and choice.
- **Democratic Management:** Cooperatives adhere to democratic management practices, ensuring that decisions are made collectively, and each member has an equal say in the governance and decision-making processes.
- **Economic Participation of Members:** Members actively participate in the economic activities of the cooperative, contributing to and benefiting from the collective endeavours of the group.
- **Education and Training:** Cooperatives often prioritize education and training for their members, aiming to enhance their skills and knowledge, fostering personal and professional development.

- **Information Sharing:** Cooperatives promote transparency and information sharing among members, facilitating an open flow of communication about the cooperative's operations, challenges, and successes.
- **Common Public Interest:** Cooperatives are driven by a common public interest, emphasizing the shared goals and benefits for their members and the broader community.

These principles play a pivotal role in the triumph of the cooperative model, fostering collaborative and sustainable business practices, enhancing member well-being, and serving the broader interests of the community. In former socialist countries like Poland, Hungary, Bulgaria, and Kazakhstan, there was sustained support for cooperatives from the socialist era. This support included maintaining their communes, preventing widespread poverty, and contributing to a steady economic growth in these nations.

Mongolia stands as a successful proponent of cooperative development both domestically and internationally, fostering collaborative ties with various nations. Notably, the Mongolian National Association of Agricultural Cooperatives has established partnerships with organizations in Japan, Korea, Thailand, Australia, Taiwan, Canada, and Sweden. Reports from the Mongolian National Association of Agricultural Cooperatives shed light on the agricultural cooperative landscape in Canada and Sweden:

- Both Canada and Sweden have embraced cooperative models in their agricultural sectors, forming the foundation for robust production development.
- Swedish cooperatives predominantly engage in agriculture, with a focus on vegetable and fruit farming.
- Canadian agricultural cooperatives participate in diverse sectors, including cattle, hog, grain, and corn farming. N. Nadmid, a distinguished Mongolian scientist and agricultural expert acquainted with Canadian cooperative practices, shared insights in an interview. He emphasized the expansive nature of Canadian financial cooperatives, resembling large banks with numerous employees. These cooperatives provide timely loans to their member cooperatives, serving as a model for Mongolia's aspirations. In Mongolia, the vision involves family farms dedicated to animal husbandry and agriculture joining forces to establish joint farm cooperatives. These joint farms would then undertake the processing of member products, supplying the processed goods to factories, exporting to foreign countries, and ultimately distributing the generated income among their members [3]. This vision aligns with the cooperative principles of collaboration, sustainable development, and shared prosperity.

Increased contributions from cooperative agricultural products play a vital role in fostering sustainable economic development within a country. Such contributions not only enhance economic stability but also provide a more resilient foundation for overcoming negative consequences arising from economic challenges, social crises, and epidemic-like diseases. The cooperative approach in agriculture becomes a strategic asset, promoting adaptability and collective resilience to various challenges that may impact the nation's well-being.

2. Historical Background, Present Status, and Emerging Trends of Cooperatives in Mongolia

Mongolia boasts a rich history of cooperative practices. Dating back to ancient times, Mongolian herding families traditionally organized themselves into neighbourhoods and collectively managed their agricultural activities. Collaborative endeavours have ingrained themselves deeply into the Mongolian way of life, as working together is essential for tasks like training animals for breeding, nurturing, and milking. Proverbs such as "a family is one life," "a single person does not make a family," "a single tree does not make a fire," and "an ocean without the strength of a crowd" echo the cultural emphasis on cooperation and collaboration.

In the early 19th century, during the reign of King Bogd, a pioneering group of citizens established Mongolia's first cooperative. According to Professor Luu Dambadorji, this landmark cooperative was founded in September

1917, driven by the initiative of Count Tsedevsuren, and was named the People's Mutual Aid Cooperative. Minister D. Chagdarjav assumed the role of the cooperative's head [4]. At that time, Chinese companies were imposing high prices on Mongolians for their goods, while acquiring livestock, meat, wool, hides, fur, and raw materials at lower rates, placing Mongolians in significant debt. The People's Mutual Aid Cooperative emerged as an initial step to liberate Mongolians from this economic predicament. Notably, King Bogd himself supported the initiative, with both the king and queen becoming members of the cooperative. The cooperative took proactive measures, establishing an initial central store in Mongolia's capital and a branch store in a border town between Russia and Mongolia. Over time, its operations expanded, and by the conclusion of 1924, the cooperative successfully provided its services to all provinces and districts. This extensive reach was achieved through 24 central stores and 95 branch stores strategically positioned throughout the country.

Researcher L. Ochirkhuyag, in his book "History of Trade and Economic Relations of Mongolia," provided insights into the remarkable progress of this cooperative. He noted, "In 1923, the cooperative accounted for 4 percent of the country's total turnover; in 1925, it surged to 24.9 percent, and by 1926, it reached 26 percent." Notably, the cooperative extended its reach beyond national borders, establishing branches in Beijing, Tianjin, Upper Ulaan-ud, and operating 14 wool washing factories and 9 wool preparation factories. The rapid development of the cooperative in this short span of time resulted in the creation of a substantial economic sector known as "Mongolian Trade," according to the statistics provided by researchers.

The second sector identified for cooperative development in Mongolia was manufacturing and services. D. Demchig, a senior industry employee, reported that production and service cooperatives adhered to cooperative rules and regulations. From 1930 to 1939, all of these cooperatives were transitioned to the organization of artels. By 1939, there were over 10,000 members across 13 provinces and 116 districts, with 147 artels in operation. These artels collectively earned an average of over 60 million MNT per year. The cooperative had evolved into a significant independent industry in Mongolia, with more than a hundred artels contributing to its growth. In their work titled "Mongolia's Light Industry Development Path," researchers Yu. Dashbal and H. Ganbaatar highlighted that the Mongolian government actively encouraged skilled individuals to work independently, share their expertise through cooperatives, engage in buying and selling activities, and collaborate in their work. This approach effectively stimulated the development of the industrial and service sectors. Referring to 1971 data, the researchers stated, "Mongolian industrial cooperatives produce products worth 277 million MNT annually, constituting approximately 20% of the total output of the industrial sector and contributing 11% to both national and local budgets. These cooperatives have become the foundation for the advancement of the Mongolian industrial sector" [6].

In Mongolia, the agricultural sector emerged as the third focal point for cooperative development. Bogd Khan recognized that the primary economic pillar for Mongolians was animal husbandry and advocated for its advancement through cooperatives. This vision was continued by the people's government, leading to the successful establishment of cooperatives in Mongolia's agricultural sector. The pastoral sector, with its unique characteristics, was deemed best suited for gradual and cooperative development rather than a centralized approach. For the cooperative development of the livestock industry, three crucial pre-defined objectives were established:

1. Ensure the health of the animals,
2. Enhance the quality of fences, water sources, animal feed, and the material base for animal husbandry, and
3. Standardize the working and living conditions of herders, transforming them into people's farmers.

These strategic measures aimed to promote the sustainable growth of the livestock industry in a manner that prioritized animal welfare, improved infrastructure, and uplifted the livelihoods of herders, aligning with the cooperative principles.

The development of agricultural cooperatives in the country is being approached through various models:

- **Simple Friendship:** This model emphasizes basic collaboration and camaraderie among individuals involved in agriculture. While it may not involve formal organizational structures, it promotes mutual support and cooperation among farmers.
- **Agricultural Cooperatives:** This model involves the formal establishment of cooperatives in the agricultural sector. These cooperatives operate based on cooperative principles, with members collectively participating in decision-making, resource-sharing, and the overall management of agricultural activities.
- **Agricultural Cooperatives in the Market Period:** This model specifically addresses the challenges and opportunities presented during market-driven periods. It likely involves adapting traditional agricultural cooperative models to align with market demands, ensuring efficiency, competitiveness, and sustainable agricultural practices in a market-oriented context.

Dr. R. Tsagaankhu, a renowned Mongolian scientist, provided insights into the development of agricultural cooperatives, highlighting their significant economic contributions. According to his review, the products generated in the agricultural sector were channelled to the state budget through taxes. The financial contributions increased over time, with figures such as 68.7 million MNT in 1965, 103.4 million MNT in 1970, and 159.9 million MNT in 1975. Notably, more than 80 percent of these contributions were attributed to Agricultural Cooperative Organizations.

Over a span of 50 years, these agricultural cooperative organizations, both directly and through other branches, have made substantial financial contributions to the state budget. Dr. Tsagaankhu estimated this cumulative contribution to be 7.1 trillion MNT, equivalent to approximately 2.7 billion American dollars in the current monetary value. This underscores the significant economic impact and sustained support provided by agricultural cooperatives to the national economy over the years.

Presently, Mongolia boasts a diverse landscape of cooperatives, reflecting a broad spectrum of economic activities. The cooperative sector comprises:

- 900 Agricultural Cooperatives
- 650 Industrial Service Cooperatives
- 525 Trade and Consumer Goods Cooperatives
- 300 Savings and Loan Cooperatives
- 285 Cooperatives in Other Fields
- 3,000 Cooperatives
- 40 Mutual Cooperatives
- 6 Professional Associations

This extensive network of cooperatives signifies the multifaceted engagement of cooperative principles in various sectors of the Mongolian economy. The active involvement of Mongolia in the international cooperative movement is regarded as a pivotal factor that will shape the nation's future development. This participation underscores the importance of collaboration, shared resources, and cooperative principles in fostering sustainable economic growth and community well-being in Mongolia.

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